

NESCent Meetings and Visitors in Years 1-4

Year	Science	Education	Informatics	Advisory	Hosted	Total	Total w/o Hosted
Yr 1 Visitors	85	15	0	28	138	266	128
Yr 1 Meetings	4	2	0	3	4	13	9
Yr 2 Visitors	288	13	16	37	174	528	354
Yr 2 Meetings	14	1	1	3	5	24	19
Yr 3 Visitors	452	98	62	23	218	853	635
Yr 3 Meetings	29	5	2	2	10	48	38
Yr 4 Visitors	379	107	29	63	80	658	578
Yr 4 Meetings	23	4	1	3	6	37	31
Yrs 1-4 Visitors	1204	233	107	151	610	2305	1695
Yrs 1-4 Meetings	70	12	4	11	25	122	97

Note: Science activities represent activities funded through our sponsored science.